

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

The UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) maintains a central global database for internationally comparable statistics in four thematic domains: (1) education, (2) science, technology and innovation, (3) culture, as well as (4) demography and socio-economics. As UNESCO's official statistical agency, the UIS compiles extensive datasets - including almost 5,000 education indicators - that underpin global monitoring of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) and inform evidence-based policymaking at national and international levels. The database is supported by detailed metadata, classification frameworks, thematic dashboards, and country profiles, with data accessible in multiple formats (CSV, Excel, JSON) together with the corresponding methodological documentation. Education constitutes by far the largest and most detailed domain in the UIS database, but data availability across countries and years remains uneven, with notable gaps in several indicators and regions. Overall, the UIS database provides broad thematic coverage and a high degree of international comparability, although limitations in temporal continuity and geographic completeness continue to restrict certain types of cross-country analyses.

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Data Review of the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) Database

The UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) Institute for Statistics (UIS) serves as an “official and trusted source of internationally comparable data on education, science, culture and communication.” (4) As UNESCO’s “official statistical agency” (4) the institution’s responsibility is the monitoring of progress on “Sustainable Development Goal 4 on Education (SDG 4)”¹ (4). The UIS collects and publicises data that underpin evidence-based policymaking and guide international and national initiatives and investments (4). The database “cover(s) over 200 countries and territories” (3: II) and “was established in 1999” (3: I). The purpose of this review² is to assess the data contained in the UIS database, not to evaluate the UNESCO Institute for Statistics as an institution.

Key Features

The UIS offers a comprehensive database that spans multiple thematic areas, covering between 12 and almost 5,000 indicators depending on the topic (11):

Table 1: Areas and Indicators Covered by the UIS

	Science, Technology and Innovation	Demography and Socio-Economics	Education	Culture
Total data points	18,862	320,056	8,166,293	6,455
Indicator count	12	35	4,919	31
Latest data release (as of October 2025)	February 2025	September 2025	September 2025	February 2025

(source: 11)

Within the educational domain, the UIS acts as the official source of SDG 4 data, providing indicators to monitor progress toward inclusive and equitable quality education (4). Table 1 illustrates this focus, as education indicators represent by far the largest share across all themes (11). Beyond education, the UIS maintains data on Research and Development (R&D) and innovation (10), as well as cultural and communication statistics (9).

The following table 2 provides a more detailed overview of which categories and themes are covered by the database:

¹ “The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015, provides a shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future. At its heart are the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which are an urgent call for action by all countries - developed and developing - in a global partnership.” (13) SDG4: “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.” (12)

² This data review has been produced by Luca-Marie Bauer (lucamar1@uni-bremen.de) as part of the Collaborative Research Center 1342 “Global Dynamics of Social Policy” at the University of Bremen.

Table 2: Categories and Themes covered by the UIS

Science, Technology and Innovation	Demography and Socio-Economics	Education	Culture
SDG9 Monitoring: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gross domestic expenditure on R&D - Researchers 	-	SDG4 Monitoring: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government expenditure on education - Basic education - Early childhood - Technical, vocational & tertiary education - Skills for employment - Equity - Youth and Adults literacy and numeracy - Education for sustainable development - School environment - Scholarships - Qualified teachers 	SDG11 Monitoring: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preserving Cultural and natural heritage - Culture 2030 Indicators (Cultural facilities; Cultural employment; International trade of cultural goods)
Other Policy Relevant Indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Female Researchers 	Policy Indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demographic indicators (Fertility rate; Life expectancy; Mortality rate; Population growth; Prevalence of HIV; Rural population; Population) - Socio-economic indicators (Total debt; GDP; PPP; Poverty headcount ratio; General government total expenditure; DEC alternative conversion factor; Official exchange rate) 	Other Policy Relevant Indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Classroom teachers and academic staff - International mobile students - Enrolment and attendance - Repetition 	-

(source: 5)

To enhance comparability and transparency, the UIS provides “metadata documents for SDG 4 indicators (including benchmark indicators) and Other Policy Relevant Indicators (OPRI)” (9), including “definition, purpose, calculation method, interpretation, type of data source, disaggregation, data required, data sources, quality assurance, limitations and comments” (9).

Furthermore, the UIS provides several tools and microsites, including:

- the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED), “provid[ing] information on national education systems” (9),
- the Education Management Information Systems (EMIS), “aim[ing] to facilitate strategic decision-making, policy formulation and budgeting [...] in helping schools and ministry of education in better managing education” (9),
- the SDG 4 Scorecard Dashboard, that “visually displays progress towards countries [with] SDG 4 benchmarks” (9),
- and Country profiles (9).

The UIS Glossary complements these datasets by providing definitions, calculation formulas, and translations in some UN languages – including “Arabic, English, French and Spanish” (9).

Data can be downloaded in CSV, Excel, or JSON formats, and can also include additional information such as metadata and footnotes (6).

Example Indicator Coverage of Discuss Data Relevant Countries

The UIS database covers a wide range of indicators across its four thematic domains. As the examples illustrated in the tables in the Appendix show, the coverage for Discuss Data relevant countries (as of November 2025) is highly uneven across topics, indicators, and years (see Appendix). Given that the dataset contains around 5,000 indicators, it was not feasible to examine all of them. Therefore, two indicators were selected for each category to assess data coverage across the 15 Discuss Data relevant countries – Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, and Uzbekistan – while acknowledging that this represents only a very small share of the available data (see Appendix).

In the field of education, which constitutes the largest share of the UIS data, indicators such as *expenditure on education as a percentage of total government expenditure* or *qualified teachers in pre-primary education* are available for most countries but often contain gaps. For example, Turkmenistan provides one observation in 2012 and only continues with observations in 2019 up until 2024, while countries like Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Kyrgyzstan offer continuous data series from the early 2000s up to 2024 and 2025 (see Appendix).

In the area of *science, technology, and innovation*, core indicators such as *GERD (Gross Domestic Expenditure on Research and Development) as a percentage of GDP* show strong temporal coverage for almost all states since 2000, whereas the indicator on *female researchers (FTE)* has substantial gaps, with several countries – including Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan – lacking data altogether (see Appendix).

Coverage becomes even more fragmented in the *culture* domain: while selected indicators such as *spending on heritage conservation* or *cultural goods exports* exist

for a few countries (e.g., Belarus, Estonia, Moldova, Ukraine) – however, with only little datapoints, many others report only single years or no data whatsoever, limiting the potential for cross-country comparisons.

The database also offers external demographic and socio-economic indicators included in the UIS Data Browser for comparison reasons, where *fertility or debt statistics* are available consistently from 2000 onward for most countries but with the *total debt* entirely missing for Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, and Russia (see Appendix).

Overall, while the UIS offers substantial thematic breadth – especially in education – the depth and continuity of indicator coverage vary significantly, with several countries showing discontinuous time series that restrict comparability across the Discuss Data region. In addition, the Data Browser interface itself limits users to viewing only six indicators simultaneously, which can further constrain large-scale comparative analyses of complex indicator sets (6).

Critique

While the UIS remains an important global source for – mainly – educational statistics, several academic evaluations over the years have highlighted persistent challenges in data quality and comparability.

Earlier critiques, such as Heyneman (1999) in *The Sad Story of UNESCO's Education Statistics*, argued that UNESCO's education data suffered from outdated technologies and inconsistent quality control (1: page 65), making cross-national comparisons unreliable for many non-OECD countries (1: pages 65, 71).

While this evaluation is very dated, it underlines structural tensions that may remain relevant when using older data. UIS has since addressed many of these issues by standardising metadata and strengthening its role as upholder of SDG 4 (3: page 30).

In recent years, the UIS has strengthened its approach to data quality by formalising tools such as the (Light) Education Data Quality Assessment Framework ((Light) Ed-DQAF), which supports countries in assessing the robustness of their administrative education data systems (7: pages 1-2).

Beginning with the September 2023 data release, the UIS also introduces a "hybrid population data policy" that enables countries to request the use of national population estimates instead of the UN Population Division's World Population Prospects (2: page 9). According to the UIS, adopting national data can "increase national ownership" (2: page 9) over the indicators and, in some cases, provide more accurate or up-to-date estimates based on improved national model specifications that incorporate information unavailable to "the UN Population Division (UNPD), which was previously the main source of population data used by the UIS" (2: page 9). At the same time, UIS acknowledges that countries with more limited "statistical capacities may not produce or update data regularly or use less appropriate model assumptions" (2: page 9). This shift furthermore raises concerns about cross-national comparability: replacing a single harmonised population source with a heterogenous set of national

estimates - applied only for countries that opt in - may complicate efforts to consistently compare SDG 4 indicators across countries.

Access

Access to the data is free of charge through the UIS Data Browser website (<https://databrowser.uis.unesco.org/>) and requires no login or registration (6).

Note

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Appendix

Example Indicator Coverage of Discuss Data Relevant Countries of UIS data (as of November 2025)

Topic: Education

Indicator 1: Expenditure on education as a percentage of total government expenditure (%) → Data source: UNESCO Institute for Statistics (8)

Indicator 2: Proportion of teachers with the minimum required qualifications in pre-primary education, both sexes (%) → Data source: UNESCO Institute for Statistics (8)

	Armenia (AM)	Azerbaijan (AZ)	Belarus (BY)	Estonia (EE)	Georgia (GE)	Kazakhstan (KZ)	Kyrgyzstan (KG)	Latvia (LV)	Lithuania (LT)	Republic of Moldova (MD)	Russian Federation (RU)	Tajikistan (TJ)	Turkmenistan (TM)	Ukraine (UA)	Uzbekistan (UZ)
Years Covered (1)	2005-2025	2000-2025	2004-2007, 2009-2024	2000-2005, 2007-2022	2000-2024	2002, 2004-2024	2000-2024	2000-2004, 2006-2022	2001-2022	2000-2024	2000-2006, 2008, 2012-2018	2000-2024	2012, 2019-2024	2000-2009, 2011-2021	2013-2024
Years Covered (2)	2002, 2009-2024	2000-2016, 2018-2024	2002-2024	No data	2000, 2002 & 2003	2014-2025	2000-2025	2010-2022	2015-2020	2019-2024	No data	2001-2016	No data	2024	2006-2023

(source: 6)

Topic: Science, Technology & Innovation

Indicator 3: GERD as a percentage of GDP → Data source: R&D surveys (8)

Indicator 4: Researchers (FTE) - % Female → Data source: R&D surveys (8)

	AM	AZ	BY	EE	GE	KZ	KG	LV	LT	MD	RU	TJ	TM	UA	UZ
Years Covered (1)	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2022	2000-2005, 2013-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2022	2000-2022	2003-2023	2000-2022	2001-2020	2015-2022	2000-2023	2000-2023
Years Covered (2)	2022 & 2023	2019-2023	2020-2023	2000-2022	2013-2023	No data	No data	2000-2022	2000-2022	2003-2023	No data	No data	No data	2007, 2016-2023	2002-2023

(source: 6)

Topic: Culture

Indicator 5: Total per capita expenditure on the preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage (constant PPP\$ - 2017) → Data source: UNESCO Institute for statistics (8)

Indicator 6: Share of exports of cultural goods in all goods Data source: UNESCO Institute for statistics (8)

	AM	AZ	BY	EE	GE	KZ	KG	LV	LT	MD	RU	TJ	TM	UA	UZ
Years Covered (1)	No data	No data	2019	2021	2020 & 2021	No data	No data	No data	No data	2023	No data	No data	2019-2021	No data	No data
Years Covered (2)	2004-2019	2004-2019	2004-2019	2004-2019	2005-2019	2004-2019	2004-2019	2004-2019	2004-2019	2004-2019	2004-2019	No data	No data	2008-2018	2017-2019

(source: 6)

Example Indicator Coverage of Discuss Data Relevant Countries of External data³ (as of November 2025)

Topic: Demographic & Socio-economic

Indicator 7: Fertility rate, total (births per woman)

Indicator 8: Total debt (% of GNI)

	AM	AZ	BY	EE	GE	KZ	KG	LV	LT	MD	RU	TJ	TM	UA	UZ
Years Covered (1)	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023
Years Covered (2)	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	No data	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	No data	No data	2000-2023	No data	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023	2000-2023

(source: 6)

³ External data covered on the UIS Data Browser website are, according to the UIS, “datasets from external sources used in the calculation [sic] our indicators”. (5)